

Factors Affecting Drug Abuse among Hostelites of Twin Cities, Pakistan

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Abstract: Drug abuse commonly refers to the use of illegal drugs that have so many negative consequences, including physical, social, and psychological drugs, and it is spreading in the world like fire. Pakistan is located in South Asia with a population of about 241.5 million, comprising about 64 % youth and nearly 25% were using some form of drugs in 2011, 240 million people were using drugs while its number increased to 296 million in 2021 which means that 1 in 17 people were using drugs in the World. This study was conducted to examine the factors that influence drug abuse in university hostels of twin cities. A quantitative cross-sectional technique was used with simple random sampling in four university hostels in twin cities. The collected data was analyzed through descriptive statistics, frequencies, and the impact of factors on dependent variables through Probit regression analysis. The results showed that the people who smoke were often moved towards drug abuse, and it is significant at 0.001(p-value), and the people with drug addict friends and smoker friends showed significant values of 0.041 and 0.002, respectively. Cannabis was the most abused drug among them, as 50% were using cannabis, and participants who were involved in extra-curricular activities or physical activities were less likely to get involved in drug abuse. There is an urgent need for policymaking to ban drugs as it is the leading cause of so many harmful activities that further impact our social, mental, and physical well-being.

Key Words: Drug Abuse, Drug Addicts, Smoking, Hostelites, Cannabis, Stress Relief

Introduction

Drug abuse commonly refers to the use of illegal drugs, which has so many negative consequences, including both physical, social, and psychological, and it is spreading in the world like fire. Drug addiction occurs when a person is habitually involved in using the drugs, which causes drug dependence in which a person is unable to quit that drug and does not remain calm without drugs. People abuse drugs due to their properties of altering the state of the brain (Ashraf Sajid., 2020), which temporarily relieves them from problems they are facing. The number of drug addicts is increasing day by day and all around the world. In 2011, 240 million people were using drugs, while this number increased to 296 million in 2021, which means that 1 in 17 people were using drugs in the World (World Drug Report, 2022)

Pakistan is located in South Asia with a population of about 241.5 million (Gallup Pakistan, 2022), which comprises about 64 % youth (The News, 2022) and nearly 25% are using some form of drugs (Masood and Sahar., 2014) which is a serious matter of concern as youth is considered as the backbone of any country and without the efforts of young generation a country will not make progress and development and if they are involved in such kind of activities where a person do not in their senses so what can a country expect from them when they are unable to anything for themselves.

The youth of Pakistan is involved in substances which include cannabis, opiates, cocaine, vape, snuff, methamphetamine, LSD, ketamine (commonly used as a safe, effective anesthetic agent, but misused as a club drug), alcohol, and many other derivatives of tobacco. In 2013, about 6.7 million population in Pakistan

were using substances other than tobacco and alcohol, according to the report of UNODC and Pakistan Bureau of Statistics 2013 (Masood et al., 2013). Now the number increased to 7.6 million, with 78% male and 22% female, with billions of dollars in narcotic trade (Al Jazeera, 2022). The number of drug addicts in Pakistan is increasing by 50,000 annually (Chuadry, Niaz, and Liaqut., 2022).

Youngsters of Pakistan aged between 15 and 19 years are extensively using cannabis in Sheesha, which is a new trend in both genders. It is praised as cool and is not considered harmful, but it contains more harmful substances, such as heavy metals and even higher concentrations of CO (carbon monoxide) than a cigarette. But it is an initial step moving forward to the use of drugs other than drug addiction and dependence. Opium is also at its peak among Pakistani drug users (Ministry of Narcotics Control, Islamabad, Year Book, 2012). In Pakistan, some drugs are traditionally used, such as opiates and cannabis, due to their cultivation in this area, and smuggling of these drugs to other countries via the routes of Pakistan further increases its usage as about 90% of world opium is produced in Afghanistan and about 40% of it is smuggled via Pakistan (Malik and Sarfraz., 2006; Latif., 2022).

There are several reasons why people abuse drugs and smoke. For one, smoking and drug abuse are often found in the same social circles. Individuals who smoke may be more likely to come in contact with individuals who use drugs, increasing their risk of exposure to drugs. Easy excess of drugs is the contributing factor to drug abuse as most of the drugs in Pakistan are available at every pan shop, such as cannabis, despite being legally banned, so every individual can buy at a very low cost no matter whether they are older or younger. Some people use drugs for pleasure and recreational purposes as they want to look cool among their friends, and also drugs change their moods and emotions, and they feel relaxed.

Students, after passing their intermediate where they live under restricted and close supervision of their parents when they join university, which is considered the creation of knowledge before that people just consume the knowledge, they get involved in extra-curricular activities and socialize with other university fellows belonging from different areas with different thoughts can also expose to several negative things and even the hostelites who have to live with other roommates with different age group and background, they also have high academic pressure so they have to manage the open life without any restrictions where they can do anything with good grades (Saeed *et al.*, 2021) due to fear of family so instead of getting into healthy activities most of the people of university particularly hostelites started using the drugs to relieve stress on temporary basis but with the passage of time some other issues may also compel them to use the drugs on daily basis. If they have a roommate who is a drug addict, they will be more likely to influence them to smoke and use drugs in a stressful situation as negative things attract quickly, and it depends on the behaviors of people and how they can handle those situations or fall into that situation. Hostelites are also more vulnerable to drug abuse than day-scholar due to a lack of checks and balances from their parents (Sarfraz and Qayyum., 2020). Even we can see school students smoking and using drugs with their friends in large numbers without any hesitation, and also the government is not taking a firm step towards the control of such things. Policies are there, but no implementation of them as the law system is not doing its job with sincerity.

Drug abuse has so many effects not just on individual life but also on their family and even society as drug abuse directly affects the health of individuals, including mental issues such as anxiety and depression (Arshad *et al.*, 2016). Most people use drugs to get rid of anxiety and depression, but in return, they can get more anxiety and depression if a person does not have drugs on a daily basis. Even though the high dose can lead to death, other physical issues may also arise, such as an imbalance in appetite, weight gain or loss, insomnia, headache, kidney and heart problems, cancer, and cognitive problems. It can destroy families and relationships as drug addicts do not take things seriously and do not pay attention to their families. Even if they

are doing the job, they lose interest and do not focus on their tasks and duties, which may result in firing from the job therefore, financial loss, which further forces them to commit crimes and get money from illegal sources, which increases the crime rate in the country. They can also share the used needles and syringes. As we can see, homeless people mostly use drugs due to the unacceptance of such people in homes and society; therefore, they are forced to leave their homes, and they start living on roadsides. Due to lack of money, they use unhygienic syringes for intake and even unhygienic living conditions, which results in HIV/AIDS and Hepatitis C, etc. Risky behaviors are also common in drug addicts, such as drinking and driving, which results in accidents. It can affect the education of an individual due to loss of interest, focus, and absenteeism, which diminishes the willpower to make progress.

Pakistan started several programs in collaboration with UNODC, including prevention and reduction of drugs and suppression of drug traffickers due to its geographic location, mainly used for smuggling to Turkey and Europe, and also the establishment of rehabilitation centers in both public and private sectors under the supervision of government which are not useful in term of complete recovery of drug addicts as after going back from rehab center they again started the drugs (Ali and Khan., 1999).

Statement of Problem

Pakistani youth are extensively involved in drug-related activities, especially those living in hostels, due to the lack of supervision of their parents and family. Even though they are well aware of the consequences of drugs, they get influenced by the bad company and start smoking with drugs. Being the hostelites for about seven years, the researcher has observed the issue of drugs in a larger number of hostelites without any checks and balances, and they are deteriorating the precious time of their life in such useless activities; therefore, the aim of this research is to explore the factors that lead the university hostelites to abuse the drugs and most consumed drug among them and this research will provide the way for policymakers to make such policies which strictly control the students to easily excess the illegal drugs available in markets even though people don't know about the factors contributing to drugs abuse so it will provide the clear understanding of factors and then by working on their government with collaboration to parents can control them to involve in such activities.

Objective

- To examine the factors that influence drug abuse among university hostelites in the Twin Cities.

Research Questions

- What are the factors that contribute to drug abuse?
- What are the reasons for drug abuse?
- Why a huge number of hostelites are involved in tobacco consumption and drugs?
- What are the main drugs of abuse among hostelites?

Methodology

Study Area and Population

The study was conducted in university hostels of Twin Cities, which includes some hostels of Rawalpindi and some of Islamabad. Twin Cities is considered the educational hub of Pakistan, with top-ranked universities including NUST, NUMS, COMSATS, IIUI, QAU, NUML, and many more, with millions of students belonging to diverse cultures. Islamabad is the capital of Pakistan and is known for its acceptance of modern ideas while sticking to its cultural heritage, while Rawalpindi is known for its oldest civilizations with the oldest

infrastructures. The population of Islamabad and Rawalpindi, according to the World Population Review (WPR), is estimated to be about 1,266,792 and 2,430,388 in 2023, respectively.

There are a lot of private hostels present in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, including university hostels of public sector universities, as private universities do not provide living facilities (DAWN, 2019), and this study targeted the university hostels, and it depends on availability and preferences of students whether they want to live in university hostel or private but due to affordability of university hostels most of the student belonging from middle-class avail this opportunity but due to larger number of students such as in QAU and IIUI students have to wait for few semesters to get the seat in hostel.

University hostels are beneficial for students in many ways as close attachment to the university will lead them to take advantage of its educational facilities, such as the library, and can learn a lot of things from books such as the famous quote of Margaret Fuller "Today a reader, tomorrow a leader." Even though they are located very close to universities, saving students precious time, they are secure mainly for female students due to the presence of security 24/7. They are also relatively cheaper than the private hostels.

Targeted Location

The time period of data collection was from June 2022 to October 2022, and the data was collected from four hostels of public sector universities, which include Arid, NUST, QAU, and IIUI.

Research Design Sampling and Size

A cross-sectional study design was adopted, and a simple random sampling technique was employed. A total of 118 respondents were taken from four universities in twin cities, and the basic purpose of this study was to investigate the factors that lead to drug abuse among hostelites and why they abused the drugs and the most abused drug among twin cities hostelites.

Data Collection

Data was collected with the help of a self-made structured questionnaire formed with the existing literature, and it had five sections: the first section contained socio-demographic characteristics of participants, which includes gender, age, education, area of residence, period of hostel, part-time job, family income, pocket money and number of family members. The second one was drug use, which covered whether they are a smoker or not, then following the drug abuse history, the type of drug they are using. The third was of factors of drug abuse, which includes the presence of smokers and drug addicts in the family and drug addict friends. Then, reasons for drug abuse which include stress relief, peer pressure, boredom, curiosity, academic pressure, and escape from personal problems. The last section contains the availability of support and resources in hostels to cope with drug addiction and abuse, which is necessary for the students if someone by chance starts following the wrong path which kind of support is present in university hostels.

Before the final collection of data, a pilot survey was conducted containing a sample size of 30 to check the mistakes and reliability of the questionnaire, and several questions were also corrected based on the respondent's confusion and capabilities even though the questionnaire was also reviewed by research supervisor and several modifications were also made for effective data collection after that questionnaire was distributed by going into university hostels and getting the data by handing over the questionnaire to respondents and also helped them clear the confusion they had while filling out the questionnaire.

The basic criteria for respondents to participate was that they should be university hostelites and be either smokers or non-smokers, but smokers were encouraged to participate; respondents could be both male or female, but due to ethics, the researcher just approached females outside the hostel by appropriately asking about the questionnaire and told them about the purpose of research, few questionnaires were given to them, and by waiting for few minutes, they filled the questionnaires from the hostels. Those who were university students but were not from university were excluded.

Data Analysis

Data obtained from respondents is analyzed with the help of a statistical package for social science SPSS (V .25). Descriptive statistics of socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, age, area of residence, period of hostel, part-time job, family income, pocket money and number of family members. After that, the impact of the dependent variable, which is drug abuse, and independent variables such as gender, area of residence, part-time job, pocket money, number of family members, smoking, smoker in the family, a drug addict in the family, drug addict in friend circle were analyzed using probit regression model due to the presence of questionnaire in dichotomous form (YES/ NO) and this model is best suitable for the survey conducted in dichotomous form. Results from the probit regression model show which variable has greater impact and which has little impact or no impact. Finally, the descriptions, graphs, and tables were used to discuss the results of this research by applying the SPSS.

Ethical Consideration

The respondents were informed about the objectives of the research and the basic purpose of this questionnaire. Written consent was taken before the collection of data, and respondents were informed that they were free to participate in the research. It was kept in mind not to add those questions that show the respondent's identity, such as they are not asked to tell their name and the name of their university.

The researcher also provided the opportunity to ask anything where they feel confused or facing difficulty at any point during the questionnaire, and they also have the right to withdraw from filling out the questionnaire at any stage where they feel uncomfortable.

Consent Form

This questionnaire is part of a research project to investigate the factors affecting drug abuse and the most abused drugs in the university hostelites of Twin City. Your participation in this questionnaire is voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw from filling this questionnaire at any time. Do not write your name anywhere on the questionnaire, as this research is highly concerned about maintaining the confidentiality of participants.

Results

Socio-demographics of Respondents

Table 1 shows different socio-demographic characteristics of a total of 118 participants (N=118), out of total 94(79.7%) were male while 24(20.3%) were female, and the participant's average age was 21.8 years old, and the age range is from 18-28 years old in which 28(23.8%) participants were between age 18 and 20, 81(68.6%) were between 21 and 24 and only 9(7.6%) were between 24 and 28 which shows that the majority of the participants were between the age 21 and 23 year old.

Table 1

Frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation of socio-demographic characteristics of participants (N=118)

Characteristics	Groups	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)	Mean (SD)
Age	18-20	28	23.8	21.8 (1.87)
	21-24	81	68.6	

	24-28	9	7.6	
Gender	Male	94	79.7	0.20 (0.40)
	Female	24	20.3	
Area of Residence	Urban	56	47.5	0.47 (0.50)
	Rural	62	52.5	
Time period of Hostel (years)	1 - 3	90	76.3	
	4 - 6	23	19.5	2.83 (1.89)
	7-10	5	4.2	
Part-time job	Yes	11	9.3	0.90 (0.29)
	No	107	90.7	
Family Income In USD	-	-	-	632.87 (859.64)
Pocket Money In USD	-	-	-	90.34 (32.62)
Number of family members	3-5	55	46.6	
	6-8	55	46.6	5.90 (1.96)
	Above 8	8	6.8	

Out of 118 respondents, 56 (47.5%) were from urban areas, while 61(52.5%) were from rural areas. The mean time period of respondents living in hostels was 2.83 years with a standard deviation(SD) of 1.89, in which 90(76.3%) had been living between 1 month to 3 years, 23(19.5%) had been living between 4 years to 6 years while remaining 5(4.2%) had been living between 7 years to 10 years.

Then, the family income of participants has a mean value of \$632.87 with an SD of \$859.64. Additionally, the Pocket money of participants has a mean value of \$90.34 with SD of \$32.62.

Out of a total, 11(9.3%) participants were doing a part-time job, while 107(90.7%) were not doing any kind of part-time job. 55(46.6%) respondents had family member between 3 to 5, another 55(46.6%) had between 6 to 8 and 8(6.8%) participants had above 8 family members.

Relationship between Smoking and DA

Figure 1

Number of DA and smoking among participants (N=118)

Figure 1 above shows the number of drug addicts, with 60(50.8%) responding with “yes” and 58(49.2%) with “No,” while 74.5% of participants were smoking and 25.5% were without smoking out of the total population. Figure 4 below shows that of all the drug addicts, 50.8% were also smokers.

Figure 2
Relationship between drug abuse and smoking

Family and Friends Involvement of Respondents in DA

Table 2 shows that 33% of participants said they have a smoker in their family, and 16.1% said that they have a drug addict in their family, while the participant also claimed that they have 90.3% of smoker friends and 42.4 % of friends who abuse the drugs.

Table 2
Family and friends' history of smoking and DA of participants

Variable	Groups	F	%	Mean (SD)
Smoker in family	Yes	33	28	0.27 (0.45)
	No	85	72	
Smoker in friends	Yes	107	90.3	0.90 (0.29)
	No	11	9.7	
Drug Addict in the family	Yes	19	16.1	0.16 (0.36)
	No	99	83.9	
Drug Addict Friend	Yes	50	42.4	0.42 (0.49)
	No	68	57.6	

Types of Drugs among Respondents

In the table below, 9.3% of participants with drug abuse claimed that they used Alcohol, 5.1% used marijuana, 1.7% used prescription drugs, 50% used cannabis, 19.5% used opium, 13.6% Ice, and 2.5% used LSDs.

Table 3
Types of drugs among DA respondents

Drug Type	Percentage (%)
Cannabis	50
Opium	19.5
Ice	13.6

Alcohol	9.3
Marijuana	5.1
Prescription drugs	1.7
LSDs	2.5

Awareness and Support System in Hostels

Table 4

Awareness about the harmful effects of drugs and the availability of support systems in university hostels

Questions	Groups	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Have you received any education or information about the health issues associated with drugs during your hostel period?	Yes	85	72
	No	33	28
Is there any support and resources available in university hostels for individuals struggling with drugs?	Yes	0	0
	No	118	100
Is there any ground available for sports in your university hostels?	Yes	118	100
	No	0	0
Are you involved in any extra-curricular activity?	Yes	44	37.3
	No	74	62.7

Questions about the awareness and availability of support systems in university hostels, as shown in the above table, showed that 72% of the participants received information and education about the harmful effects of drugs while living in the hostel. 100% of participants claimed that they don't have any kind of support system for drug addicts in their hostels. 100% of participants said they have grounds for sports near their hostels, while 37.3% said they are involved in extra-curricular activities.

The regression model provides a good fit for pseudo-R² of about (0.725) with a high significant value of the chi-square test as $p < 0.0001$ which, which means that this model provides a significant variation in independent variables related to drug abuse.

The following table shows the coefficients, standard error, z-stats, and p-values of the independent variables linked to drug abuse. Gender had a regression coefficient of -0.007 with a value of 0.991, which did not show any significance. The regression coefficient for age was -0.351, which was significant at 10%, which means that a year increase in age will decrease the chances of drug abuse by 0.351%. Education is also significant at 10%, with a value of 0.088 and a regression coefficient of 0.498. The hostel time period of participants also showed a significant value of 5% (0.022) with a regression coefficient of 0.355, which means that staying in hostels for longer periods will increase the risks of drug abuse. Family income had a regression coefficient of 0.0003, which was insignificant. The pocket money of participants was also not significant, with a regression coefficient of 8.82 and a p-value of 0.811.

Household size or no. of family members had a regression coefficient of -0.126 with a value of 0.315, which was also insignificant. The residency included urban and rural, which was also insignificant, with a regression coefficient of -0.067 with a p-value of 0.894. The part-time jobs of respondents also showed a negative sign, with a coefficient of -0.564 and an insignificant value of 0.461. The regression coefficient of variable smokers in the respondent's family member showed -1.19, which was significant at 10% (0.086),

while drug addicts in the family were insignificant (0.500) with a coefficient of 0.630. Furthermore, smoking among friends had a strong significant value at 1% with a coefficient of 2.286 and p-value of 0.002, while the regression coefficient of drug addiction among friends was 0.922, which was a 10% significant (0.041).

The regression coefficient of a participant who smoked was 2.405, which was significant at 1% (0.001), which means those who smoked will become a drug addict at later stages. Awareness about the negative impacts of drugs on health had a coefficient of 0.775, which was not significant (0.204), which means that respondents, despite knowing its negative outcome, indulged in drug abuse. Extra-curricular activities had a regression coefficient of -3.25, which means if extra-curricular activities increase, drug abuse decreases, which was significant at 1% (0.000).

Table 5*Probit regression analysis*

Variables	Coefficients	Std. Err.	Z	p
Constant	-3.817	2.744	-1.39	0.164
Gender	-0.0074	0.652	-0.01	0.991
Age	-0.351	0.201	-1.75	0.081*
Education	0.498	0.292	1.71	0.088*
Hostel time period	0.355	0.155	2.29	0.022**
Family income	0.0003	0.001	0.32	0.752
Pocket money	8.82e-06	0.000036	0.24	0.811
Household size	-0.126	0.126	-1.00	0.315
Residency	-0.067	0.5055	-0.13	0.894
Part-time job	-0.564	0.764	-0.74	0.461
Smoker in family	-1.199	0.698	-1.72	0.086*
A drug addict in the family	0.630	0.935	0.67	0.500
Smoker in friends	2.286	0.731	3.13	0.002***
Drug addict among friends	0.922	0.451	2.04	0.041**
Smoking	2.450	0.767	3.19	0.001***
Awareness	0.775	0.610	1.27	0.204
Extra-curricular activities	-3.258	2.744	-1.39	0.000***

Note: *, **, and *** indicates significance at 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively.

No of obs = 118

LR chi² = 118.63

Pseudo R² = 0.725

Prob > chi² = 0.0000

Log-likelihood = -22.458

Reasons for DA among Respondents

In the table below, among the drug abuse participants, 42.4% claimed that they started the drugs because of stress relief, 26.3% due to peer pressure, 13.6% due to boredom, 14.4% curiosity, 11.9% socializing, 8.5% said due to academic pressure and 14.4% claimed due to escape from personal problems.

Table 6*Reasons for DA among DA Respondents*

Reasons	Percentage (%)
Stress Relief	42.4
Peer Pressure	26.3
Escape from Personal Problems	14.4
Curiosity	14.4
Boredom	13.6
Socializing	11.9
Academic Pressure	8.5

Discussion

An increasing number of drug addicts in university hostelites poses a serious threat to academic progress, which is the base for their employment status in the future. They are becoming useless and do not remain in their senses after getting into addictions, but they are considered the future of the country. Most of the hostelites are first involved in light drugs such as tobacco, and then they move towards strong drugs such as cannabis, opium, alcohol, LSD, etc., and most of them are multiple drug users. They can switch from one drug to another, or they can use multiple drugs at the same time (Ikoh et al., 2019; Gjeruldsen et al., 2006).

The findings of this research reveal that smoking and drug abuse have a very close connection as each respondent with drug abuse was also a smoker, even though there were 90 smokers out of 118 respondents from university hostels, which means that they are also at risk to starting the drug abuse and regression analysis also showed the very significant relation of smoking and drug abuse (Shafiq et al., 2006).

This study did not show any significant relation between drug abuse education and residency of respondents, but it was well known that the age group of this study was mostly between 19 and 24 as all were in their youth stage, and it is also commonly known that having high education people were unlikely to get involved in drug abuse but this study showed very little significant and residency of hostelites did not have any impact on drug abuse as a common belief about the rural that they have less exposure and therefore they may greatly involve in drug abuse, but they are equally involved with urban background, and these findings are similar to the findings of Pagare et al., (2004) which showed that education and urban background were insignificant with drug abuse.

Age in this research showed significant values that were negative, which means that with the increase in age, there were fewer chances of people being involved in drug abuse. So, the teenage years are a crucial time period when most people indulge in harmful activities. If this threshold passes, there are few chances of starting these activities, and when people are growing in age and in Pakistani society, they have to start their job and earn their living while in university life, they have full support from their parents and after graduation, they have to start anything which keeps them busy so they have very less time to think about such activities so there would be fewer chances that they start drug abuse in old ages.

Family background was another factor, and drug addicts in family members did not show any significant relation with drug abuse in contrast to a previous study by Grichting and Barber., (1989) which revealed that the person who had a drug addict in the family had a great influence on others to start the drug abuse, but this research just showed that the everybody among participants had drug addict friend so peer pressure can be the reason according to the study of Gossop et al., (1989) and Johnston., (2000), but the main reasons in this study was stress relief following the peer pressure and curiosity.

About 72% of respondents said they had received the information and had awareness about the harmful effects of drug abuse, but despite having the awareness, they abused the drugs, which means that awareness just in the form of a seminar is not enough. Rather, they need behavior change therapies to include healthy activities in their early life so that they keep themselves busy and do not move towards such activities, but the findings of Zaman et al. (2015) stated that lack of information and awareness about harmful effects may leads to the drug abuse but this research contrast that findings.

Household income and pocket money in this research did not show any significance, but previous studies such as (Nazish et al. Zaman et al., 2015) showed that students of private universities who are wealthier than the public sector universities are more prone to use illegal drugs, but we can see the beggars who take drugs try to get money by theft and by doing other crimes just for the sake of making money to fulfill their urge for drugs and homeless people were once had the homes but due to such activities they are kicked from their homes, and they share syringes, drugs do crimes and get several diseases including hepatitis, AIDs, and cancer etc. The study of Foo et al. (2012) showed that the children who are forced to do child labor because of poverty and their social mixing and gathering with different kinds of people with different backgrounds copy their habits and become involved in drug trafficking and smuggling, which is easy to make money but with that easiness ruin of life is also there. Other reasons for drug abuse selected by the participants in this research were escape from personal problems following curiosity, boredom, socializing, and academic pressure.

Participants who were involved in extra-curricular activities were less likely to abuse drugs as in this research, drug abuse, and extra-curricular activities showed a very strong relationship, and only a few of them were involved in sports or extra-curricular as participating in sports and extra-curricular activities kept the students busy in their free time and they use their energy in positive way even though they make their friends in such society who have healthy living style and by choosing such lifestyle they can stay active in academia and can have good grades which are necessary in getting the good job and taking admission in higher education in top ranked universities.

Part-time jobs did not show any significant relation, but it can be considered as a good opportunity for students to keep busy and earn their living on their own and become independent during university life, which helps them in hunting for jobs after graduation very easily as they already make many connections while taking home tuition, working in software house, working at restaurants, etc. and they also learn a lot of positive things by working as a part-time which help them in making good progress in their class.

Cannabis was chosen as the most abused drug due to its easy accessibility and cheaper in Pakistan, and almost in every shop, you can find it without any restrictions 50% of the drugs abused were cannabis, followed by opium, ice, alcohol, marijuana, prescription drugs, and LSDs.

Limitations

This research is limited in terms of generalizability as it is a cross-sectional study in which data was collected during a specific period of time and from twin cities of Pakistan, so these findings will not be applicable internationally or nationally to other areas even on hostels other than university hostels of the twin city. The sample size is also kept very small due to constraints of time and resources, so the researcher did not take a different approach to get maximum data by covering each university hostel and conducting a comparative study of private hostels vs. university hostels. Researcher biases and respondent biases were also present as the researcher may include several questions and discuss according to his thoughts, and respondents

respond in their own way or according to the situation they were facing during the completion of the questionnaire.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Nowadays, every gender in their youth, due to lack of opportunities and absence of guidelines to make choices in their lives, are facing issues of depression and anxiety, and these are the main factors towards the onset of these harmful behaviors. The results of this study explore several factors related to drug abuse among young people living in university hostels. Efforts made by policymakers in this population could help to prevent drug abuse and its associated negative consequences. Further research is also needed to fully understand the different factors and reasons for drug abuse and to identify potential strategies for preventing drug abuse. Regardless of these factors, it is clear that drug abuse is a dangerous and unhealthy habit that can have serious negative consequences on physical and mental health. Therefore, it is important for individuals to be aware of the risks associated with it and to take steps to protect their health.

Based on the results of this paper, several recommendations are made, which are the following: -

- First of all, mental health is necessary, so there should be a psychosocial support system in every university hostel that deals with stress and anxiety and behavior therapies to reduce them in a healthy way so there will be fewer chances that hostelites indulge in such activities just to relieve stress.
- There should be a complete ban on products that promote drug abuse, such as cigarettes, nicotine pouches, cannabis, opium, alcohol, LSD, etc.
- There should be strong policies and social action programs for the control of drugs.
- The government should hold accountable the drug traffickers and smugglers and seize the sites where they are grown. If there is no supply, no demand will occur.
- Awareness campaigns about the harmful effects of drugs are necessary for schools and colleges, especially for parents, so that they engage their children in healthy activities in childhood.
- Parents should keep an eye on and observe the activities of their children, and if they show some sign of drug abuse, parents should guide them in a polite manner.
- Drug education should be introduced in the curriculum so that students are aware of illicit drugs and their harmful effects on individual health and negative effects on family and relationships.
- The government should provide opportunities for students to take part in sports and there should be sports grounds in every area and to ensure the availability of grounds in every area as most people do not go for physical activities just because of the longer distance of grounds from their homes.
- There should be in-depth research on the number of drug addicts and the people who are prone to drug abuse, and designing, implementing, and modification of policies should occur on a regular basis.

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